

The Premonstratensian Order in the Middle Ages

also known as “The Order of Prémontré”, “Norbertines”, “The White Canons”

By Yvonne Seale, SUNY Geneseo

Entry tags: Reform Movement, Roman Catholic, Religious Group, Monasticism, Medieval Christianity

The Premonstratensians are a reformed monastic order which emerged in northern France in the first quarter of the twelfth century. From the mother abbey of Prémontré, which was established under the leadership of Norbert of Xanten (c. 1075-1134) and Hugues of Fosses (c. 1093-1164), the order spread widely across Europe during the twelfth and thirteenth centuries. The Premonstratensians observed the Rule of St Augustine, with significant influence from the Cistercian Order in terms of their mode of life and internal governance. The male members of the order were canons; while in some parts of Europe such as France, they often practiced a more contemplative form of life, in other regions they were frequently involved in pastoral care and preaching. In what is today northeastern Europe and western Poland, they played a prominent role in the conversion of peoples there to Christianity. Women were prominent members of the order in the first two centuries or so of its existence. They generally referred to themselves as “sisters” rather than as “canonesses”, however. Premonstratensian communities were organized in a number of circaries, roughly equivalent to ecclesiastical provinces.

Date Range: 1120 CE - 2023 CE

Region: The Abbey of Prémontré

Region tags: Europe, Western Europe, France

The location of the mother abbey of Prémontré.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ardura, Bernard. *Prémontrés: histoire et spiritualité*. CERCOR Travaux et recherches 7. Saint-Etienne: Publications de l'Université de Saint-Etienne, 1995.
- Source 2: Backmund, Norbert. *Monasticon Praemonstratense id est, Historia circariarum atque canoniarum candidi et canonici Ordinis Praemonstratensis*. 3 vols. Straubing: Cl. Attenkofersche Buchdruckerei, 1949.
- Source 3: Leinsle, Ulrich. *Die Prämonstratenser. Geschichte der christlichen Orden*. Stuttgart: Kohlhammer Verlag, 2020.
- Source 1: Seale, Yvonne and Heather Wacha. *The Cartulary of Prémontré*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2023.
- Source 2: Antry, Theodore J. and Carol Neel. *Norbert and early Norbertine spirituality*. New York: Paulist

Press, 2007.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://yvonnesseale.org/blog/2019/11/28/handlist-of-premonstratensian-cartularies/>
- Source 1 Description: Handlist of Premonstratensian cartularies
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.snc.edu/cns/research/>
- Source 2 Description: The website for the Center for Norbertine Studies
- Source 3 URL: <https://digital-exhibits.library.nd.edu/4e1e9c97ed/prmontr-architectural-sites>
- Source 3 Description: This database provides access to nearly 800 early 20th-century photographs that document architectural sites sponsored by the Order of Prémontré.
- Source 1 URL: <https://dissinet.cz/maps/premonstratensiansfrance/>
- Source 1 Description: Map of Premonstratensian communities in France

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/001640524>
- Source 1 Description: An edition of the Cartulary of Cockersand Abbey in three volumes.
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.attalus.org/armenian/hetumtoc.html>
- Source 2 Description: Het'um the Historian's History of the Tartars (also known as The Flower of Histories of the East), an account written by an Armenian royal who joined the Premonstratensian Order.
- Source 3 URL: https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_7w2F-OMN7C4C
- Source 3 Description: Charles-Louis Hugo, "Sacri et canonici Ordinis Praemonstratensis annales", 2 vols. (1734)

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Premonstratensians used the same scriptures as other Western Christians during this period: the Christian Bible, consisting of the Old and New Testament.

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: A number of Premonstratensian communities had their own scriptorium (room or space set aside for the production of manuscripts), where copies of the scriptures were often created. Both male and female members of the order could take part in the copying and decoration of such manuscripts, or as in the case of the double abbey of Schäftlarn, collaborated in manuscript production. (Beach, 104-127) Some of the manuscripts created by the order number among the

masterpieces of medieval art, such as the monumental Floreffe Bible, one of the most significant books produced in the Meuse region in the 12th century.

Reference: Beach, Alison I.. *Women as Scribes: Production and Monastic Reform in Twelfth-century Bavaria*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009.

Reference: Chapman, Gretel. "The Floreffe Bible Revisited" 35, no. 2 (July 1991).
<https://doi.org/10.1484/j.j.mss.3.1367>.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

Notes: However, interpretations that were considered to be outside of the mainstream could be considered heretical.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Contact with other religions depended according to region. Premonstratensian houses in some parts of Western Europe and the Mediterranean Basin came into contact with Jewish communities; those founded in the Eastern Mediterranean during the Crusades would also have come into contact with Muslim communities.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Conversion to Christianity was welcomed and sometimes coerced by the church during the Middle Ages. A text produced at the Premonstratensian monastery of Cappenberg ca. 1200 purports to be the autobiography of a Jew, Herman, who converted to Christianity and entered the religious life as a Premonstratensian. Historians debate whether Herman ever existed, or whether he was the invention of a Christian writer, but the text was undoubtedly written to promote conversion—whether of Jews to Christianity or Christians to a more rigorous form of religious life.

Reference: Abulafia, Anna Sapir. "The Ideology of Reform and Changing Ideas Concerning Jews in the Works of Rupert of Deutz and Hermannus Quondam Iudeus" 7, no. 1 (March 1993). <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01674494>.

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Reference: Hames, Harvey J.. "'ante Omnia, Fratres Carissimi, Diligatur Deus, Deinde Proximus': Herman/Judah's *Opusculum De Conversione Sua* Re-examined". In *Conflict and Religious Conversation in Latin Christendom: Studies in Honour of Ora Limor*. Turnhout: Brepols, 2014.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: A number of Premonstratensians were involved in antisemitic actions and rhetoric during the Middle Ages. A “hermit from a Premonstratensian canonry” urged on the mob during the massacre of the Jewish community of York, England, in 1190 (Dobson, 18) while German Premonstratensians were prominent in spreading the antisemitic myth of the Blood Libel (Madigan, 349).

Reference: Dobson, Richard Barrie. *The Jewish Communities of Medieval England: The Collected Essays of R.B. Dobson*. York: Borthwick Institute, 2010.

Reference: Madigan, Kevin. *Medieval Christianity*. Yale University Press, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.12987/9780300158878>.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: While the Premonstratensians generally confined their activities to Christian-majority areas during the Middle Ages, their presence in the Crusader kingdoms did mean that they were there during times of conflict. In 1187, many members of the order were killed during the fall of the Kingdom of Jerusalem, while in 1291, a number of Premonstratensians of the abbey of St John were killed during the fall of the city of Acre. Their fellow Premonstratensians regarded them as martyrs for their faith.

Reference: Jotischky, Andrew, and Bernard Hamilton. “The Premonstratensian Canons”. In *Latin and Greek Monasticism in the Crusader States*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Those joining religious communities generally promised to follow their community's rule/statutes and often made solemn (permanent) vows of poverty, chastity, and obedience. In the late 12th century, those entering the religious life at the Scottish Premonstratensian abbey of Dryburgh made the following vow: I, brother N., offer myself to the church of the blessed Mary, mother of God, and of Saint John the Baptist of Prémontré. I promise my moral conversion and stability in the place according to the Gospel of Christ, the apostolic institution, and the canonical Rule of Saint Augustine. I promise obedience to lord N., father of this church, and to his successors whom the most irreproachable members of this community will elect. (*Patrologia Latina*, 198:479-480)

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: In theory, social class was not a factor in whether someone could become a Premonstratensian. However, in practice those of higher social class—those with literacy skills, or who could bring property with them on their entry into the religious life—tended to become canons (if men) or (choir) sisters (if women). Those of lower social class backgrounds tended to become conversi/lay brothers and sisters.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There was no specific age at which a novice was required to make their full monastic profession. However, by the late thirteenth century, the general consensus among canon (church) lawyers was that boys needed to be fourteen and girls twelve before they entered the novitiate. (Makowski, 29)

Reference: Makowski, Elizabeth. *Apostate Nuns in the Later Middle Ages*. Woodbridge, UK: Boydell and Brewer, 2019.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Both men and women could join the Premonstratensian Order.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: At the end of a novitiate period, novices took solemn (formal) vows which made them full members of the order.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Religious architecture varied according to function and region. While there could be some similarities between different Premonstratensian communities, the order did not have a single set architectural style. Some abbeys were built in the Romanesque style, some in the Gothic, and some in a blend of the two. The church of Milevsko (Czechia) is largely Romanesque, while that of Altenberg (Germany) is largely Gothic. The Romanesque chapel of the women's community of Chéry-Chartreuve (France) is representative of the kinds of places of worship used by smaller Premonstratensian communities. Many French houses in particular were partially or entirely rebuilt in the 17th and 18th centuries in the Baroque style. The famous library of Strahov Abbey, Prague, is a Baroque structure.

Reference: Clark, William W.. "Cistercian Influences on Premonstratensian Church Planning: Saint-martin at Laon". In *Studies in Cistercian Art and Architecture*. Kalamazoo, MI: Cistercian Publications, 1984.

Reference: Bonnet, Philippe. *Les Constructions De L'ordre De Prémontré En France Aux Xviiie Et Xviiiie Siècles*. Geneva: Librairie Droz, 1983.

Reference: Petit, François. "Le Puritanisme Des Premiers Prémontrés Dans L'architecture Monastique Au Xiiie Siècle". In *L'architecture Monastique: Actes Et Travaux De La Rencontre Franco-allemande Des Historiens D'art.*, Mainz: Service des relations artistiques de la Direction générale des affaires culturelles, 1951.

Reference: Clapham, A.W.. "Vi.—<i>the Architecture of the Premonstratensians, with Special Reference to Their Buildings in England</i>" 73 (1923). <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0261340900010316>.

Reference: Dauzet, Dominique-Marie. "L'architecture Prémontrée Dans L'Espagne Médiévale: Recherches Et Premiers Bilans". *Analecta Praemonstratensia* 76 (2000): 307-17.

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Premonstratensian churches could be home to elaborate tombs and/or tombstones in

the Middle Ages. Some commemorated significant abbots, abbesses or bishops of the order. Others were erected for important patrons/donors of the order, who chose to be buried in a Premonstratensian church in return for their benefaction. The abbey church of Braine (France) was for many generations the necropolis of the counts of Braine and Dreux, while the abbey church of Altenberg (Germany) contains the effigy tomb of Abbess Gertrude.

Reference: Bur, Michel. "Une Célébration Sélective De La Parentèle. Le Tombeau De Marie De Dreux À Saint-yved De Braine, Xiiie Siècle" 135, no. 2 (1991). <https://doi.org/10.3406/crai.1991.14973>.

Reference: Rorimer, James J.. "Four Tombs from Las Avellanas and Other Gothic Sculptures" 8, no. 8 (April 1950). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3257494>.

Reference: Teuscher, Andrea. Das Prämonstratenserkloster Saint-yved in Braine Als Grablege Der Grafen Von Dreux: Zu Stifterverhalten Und Grabmalgestaltung Im Frankreich Des 13. Jahrhunderts. Bamberg: Lehrstuhl I für Kunstgeschichte und Aufbaustudium Denkmalpflege an der Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg, 1990.

Reference: Schuffels, Christian. "'beata Gerdrudis, Filia Sancte Elyzabet': Gertrud, Die Tochter Der Heiligen Elisabeth, Und Das Prämonstratenserinnenstift Altenberg an Der Lahn". In Die Fürstin Der Armen : Reisen Zur Heiligen Elisabeth - Ungarische Königstochter, Thüringer Landgräfin, Europäische Heilige ; 1207-1231. Erfurt: Verl. d. Thüringer Allgemeine, 2007.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– No

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Premonstratensian brothers and sisters gathered together daily in the chapterhouse (or equivalent communal room if a small community), and could also gather in the cloister.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population,

numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:
– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:
– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:
– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:
– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
– Yes

Notes: Monarchs and regional rulers frequently made donations to religious orders such as the Premonstratensians in order to build/renovate structures or to endow chapels and benefices.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:
– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
– Yes

Notes: Secular government could be called on by monastic communities to enforce their rules at times, such as ensuring that apostate monastics (those who had left their houses without institutional and/or papal permission) would be forced to return.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Notes: The kinds of iconography present in art produced by/for Premonstratensians in the Middle Ages is largely within the mainstream of contemporary Western Christian artistic traditions, though with particular emphases on e.g. depictions of St. Norbert venerating the Eucharist, a reference to his debates with the heretic Tanchelm of Antwerp.

Reference: Stahlheber, Renate. "Die Ikonographie Norberts Von Xanten: Themen Und Bildwerke". In Norbert Von Xanten. Adliger, Ordensstifter, Kirchenfürst. Cologne, 1984.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– No

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Physical, emotional, or spiritual torments were believed to be consequences that could be visited on apostates during their lifetime.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: It is customary for Christian churches to be oriented west-east with the altar/sanctuary at the eastern end of the building.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

- ↳ A single leader of a local community:
 - Yes
- ↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:
 - No
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - No
 - ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - Yes
 - ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - No
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Premonstratensians undertook pilgrimages to places such as the Holy Land, as was the case in 1137/38 with Jindřich (Henry) Zdík, a member of the Order who was also bishop of Olomouc.

Premonstratensian houses could also function either as the destinations for Christian pilgrims, or as resting places for those on their way to major pilgrimage hubs such as Santiago de Compostela.

Reference: Wolverton, Lisa Ann. "Henry Zdík, Bishop of Olomouc and Premonstratensian". In *Portraits of Medieval Eastern Europe, 900-1400*. New York: Routledge, 2018.

Reference: Ardura, Bernard. "Saint Norbert, Le Pèlerin". In *Medioevo in Cammino: L'europa Dei Pellegrini : Atti Del Convegno Internazionale Di Studi, Orta San Giulio, 2-5 Settembre 1987*. San Giulio: Comune di Orta San Giulio, 1989.

Reference: Fourcade, Jean. "Les Pèlerins De Saint-jacques De Compostelle Sur La Route Du Littoral: Le Prieuré Hôpital Saint-jacques De Zuberno". *Société Des Sciences, Lettres Et Arts De Bayonne New Series*, no. 119 (1968): 805-22.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Contact with other religions depended according to region. Premonstratensian houses in some parts of Western Europe and the Mediterranean Basin came into contact with Jewish communities; those founded in the Eastern Mediterranean during the Crusades would also have come into contact with Muslim communities.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Conversion to Christianity was welcomed and sometimes coerced by the church during the Middle Ages. A text produced at the Premonstratensian monastery of Cappenberg ca. 1200 purports to be the autobiography of a Jew, Herman, who converted to Christianity and entered the religious life as a Premonstratensian. Historians debate whether Herman ever existed, or whether he was the invention of a Christian writer, but the text was undoubtedly written to promote conversion—whether of Jews to Christianity or Christians to a more rigorous form of religious life.

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↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

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Notes: A number of Premonstratensians were involved in antisemitic actions and rhetoric during the Middle Ages. A “hermit from a Premonstratensian canony” urged on the mob during the massacre of the Jewish community of York, England, in 1190 (Dobson, 18) while German Premonstratensians were prominent in spreading the antisemitic myth of the Blood Libel (Madigan, 349).

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↳ Assigned by gender:

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Notes: Both men and women could join the Premonstratensian Order.

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Notes: At the end of a novitiate period, novices took solemn (formal) vows which made them full members of the order.

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– No

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– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

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Notes: Monarchs and regional rulers frequently made donations to religious orders such as the Premonstratensians in order to build/renovate structures or to endow chapels and benefices.

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

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Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

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Nature of religious group [please select one]:

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- ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - No
- ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - No
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Premonstratensians used the same scriptures as other Western Christians during this period: the Christian Bible, consisting of the Old and New Testament.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: A number of Premonstratensian communities had their own scriptorium (room or space set aside for the production of manuscripts), where copies of the scriptures were often created. Both male and female members of the order could take part in the copying and decoration of such manuscripts, or as in the case of the double abbey of Schäftlarn, collaborated in manuscript production. (Beach, 104-127) Some of the manuscripts created by the order number among the masterpieces of medieval art, such as the monumental Floreffe Bible, one of the most significant books produced in the Meuse region in the 12th century.

Reference: Beach, Alison I.. *Women as Scribes: Production and Monastic Reform in Twelfth-century Bavaria*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009.

Reference: Chapman, Gretel. “The Floreffe Bible Revisited” 35, no. 2 (July 1991).
<https://doi.org/10.1484/j.mss.3.1367>.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

Notes: However, interpretations that were considered to be outside of the mainstream could be considered heretical.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Religious architecture varied according to function and region. While there could be some similarities between different Premonstratensian communities, the order did not have a single set architectural style. Some abbeys were built in the Romanesque style, some in the Gothic, and some in a blend of the two. The church of Milevsko (Czechia) is largely Romanesque, while that of Altenberg (Germany) is largely Gothic. The Romanesque chapel of the women's community of Chéry-Chartreuve (France) is representative of the kinds of places of worship used by smaller Premonstratensian communities. Many French houses in particular were partially or entirely rebuilt in the 17th and 18th centuries in the Baroque style. The famous library of Strahov Abbey, Prague, is a Baroque structure.

Reference: Clark, William W.. "Cistercian Influences on Premonstratensian Church Planning: Saint-martin at Laon". In *Studies in Cistercian Art and Architecture*. Kalamazoo, MI: Cistercian Publications, 1984.

Reference: Bonnet, Philippe. *Les Constructions De L'ordre De Prémontré En France Aux Xviie Et Xviiiè Siècles*. Geneva: Librairie Droz, 1983.

Reference: Petit, François. "Le Puritanisme Des Premiers Prémontrés Dans L'architecture Monastique Au Xiie Siècle". In *L'architecture Monastique: Actes Et Travaux De La Rencontre Franco-allemande Des Historiens D'art*. Mainz: Service des relations artistiques de la Direction générale des affaires culturelles, 1951.

Reference: Clapham, A.W.. "The Architecture of the Premonstratensians, with Special Reference to Their Buildings in England" 73 (1923). <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0261340900010316>.

Reference: Dauzet, Dominique-Marie. "L'architecture Prémontrée Dans L'espace Médiévale: Recherches Et Premiers Bilans". *Analecta Praemonstratensia* 76 (2000): 307-17.

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Premonstratensian churches could be home to elaborate tombs and/or tombstones in the Middle Ages. Some commemorated significant abbots, abbesses or bishops of the order. Others were erected for important patrons/donors of the order, who chose to be buried in a Premonstratensian church in return for their benefaction. The abbey church of Braine (France) was for many generations the necropolis of the counts of Braine and Dreux, while the abbey church of Altenberg (Germany) contains the effigy tomb of Abbess Gertrude.

Reference: Bur, Michel. "Une Célébration Sélective De La Parentèle. Le Tombeau De Marie De Dreux À Saint-yved De Braine, Xiiiè Siècle" 135, no. 2 (1991). <https://doi.org/10.3406/crai.1991.14973>.

Reference: Rorimer, James J.. "Four Tombs from Las Avellanas and Other Gothic Sculptures" 8, no. 8 (April 1950). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3257494>.

Reference: Teuscher, Andrea. Das Prämonstratenserklöster Saint-yved in Braine Als Grablege Der Grafen Von Dreux: Zu Stifterverhalten Und Grabmalgestaltung Im Frankreich Des 13. Jahrhunderts. Bamberg: Lehrstuhl I für Kunstgeschichte und Aufbaustudium Denkmalpflege an der Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg, 1990.

Reference: Schuffels, Christian. "beata Gerdrudis, Filia Sancte Elyzabet': Gertrud, Die Tochter Der Heiligen Elisabeth, Und Das Prämonstratenserinnenstift Altenberg an Der Lahn". In Die Fürstin Der Armen : Reisen Zur Heiligen Elisabeth - Ungarische Königstochter, Thüringer Landgräfin, Europäische Heilige ; 1207-1231. Erfurt: Verl. d. Thüringer Allgemeine, 2007.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– No

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Premonstratensian brothers and sisters gathered together daily in the chapterhouse (or equivalent communal room if a small community), and could also gather in the cloister.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Notes: The kinds of iconography present in art produced by/for Premonstratensians in the Middle Ages is largely within the mainstream of contemporary Western Christian artistic traditions, though with particular emphases on e.g. depictions of St. Norbert venerating the Eucharist, a reference to his debates with the heretic Tanchelm of Antwerp.

Reference: Stahlheber, Renate. "Die Ikonographie Norberts Von Xanten: Themen Und Bildwerke". In Norbert Von Xanten. Adliger, Ordensstifter, Kirchenfürst. Cologne, 1984.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: It is customary for Christian churches to be oriented west-east with the altar/sanctuary at the eastern end of the building.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Premonstratensians undertook pilgrimages to places such as the Holy Land, as was the case in 1137/38 with Jindřich (Henry) Zdík, a member of the Order who was also bishop of Olomouc. Premonstratensian houses could also function either as the destinations for Christian pilgrims, or as resting places for those on their way to major pilgrimage hubs such as Santiago de Compostela.

Reference: Wolverson, Lisa Ann. "Henry Zdík, Bishop of Olomouc and Premonstratensian". In *Portraits of Medieval Eastern Europe, 900-1400*. New York: Routledge, 2018.

Reference: Ardura, Bernard. "Saint Norbert, Le Pèlerin". In *Medioevo in Cammino: L'europa Dei Pellegrini : Atti Del Convegno Internazionale Di Studi, Orta San Giulio, 2-5 Settembre 1987*. San Giulio: Comune di Orta San Giulio, 1989.

Reference: Fourcade, Jean. "Les Pélerins De Saint-jacques De Compostelle Sur La Route Du Littoral: Le Prieuré Hôpital Saint-jacques De Zuberno". *Société Des Sciences, Lettres Et Arts De Bayonne New*

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Optional (common)

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

- ↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans’ behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

- ↳ Food:

– Yes

- ↳ Sacred space(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
- ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: Sodomy; extra-marital sex
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No
 - Notes: Dependent on context, e.g. jousting.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Yes, within medieval Christian understandings of social hierarchy/rank.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Mainstream Christian belief is that Jesus Christ was the Messiah, and that his eventual return will usher in a Messianic Age and the world to come.

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Exists as part of a Trinity (Father, Son, Spirit); Creator God.
 - Notes: The tenets of Western Christian beliefs about the nature of the deity are laid out in e.g. the Nicene Creed.
 - Reference: The Council of Nicea. "The Nicene Creed", 1996. <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/source/nicenecreed.asp>.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Medieval Christians generally believed in the omniscience of God.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Mystical ecstasies; interpretation of signs and portents such as earthquakes, volcanic eruptions.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
 - ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– No

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Masses and prayers were said annually for deceased members of the order, the number of which varied from community to community. According to the earliest surviving Premonstratensian ordinary, which was in use 13-14th centuries, specifies that for the first year after the death of a member of the order, he or she was to be prayed for daily, while each member of their community undertook a period of penance on their behalf. Vigil masses were to be celebrated on the 7th, 30th, and one-year anniversary of their death, while various memorial privileges were also celebrated in other Premonstratensian communities.

Reference: Lefèvre, Placide. *L'ordinaire De Prémontré D'après Des Manuscrits Du Xiie Et Du Xiiie Siècle*. Louvain: Bureaux de la Revue, 1941.

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Interment was the standard mode of burial for medieval Christians. Premonstratensian customs allowed for various people to be buried within the boundaries of one of their communities: a member of the order, including those who joined *ad succurendum* (on their deathbed), those who were members of affiliated fraternities, those who died while within the boundaries of the monastic community, and those patrons of the community who expressed a wish to be buried in a Premonstratensian community.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Some members of the order, particularly heads of a community, might be buried with a seal-ring or seal-die or other symbol of office.

↳ Valuable items:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Some deceased members of the order were buried within the confines of their community's church itself, a burial location considered to be particularly spiritually efficacious.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

Reference: Bischoff, Guntram. “Early Premonstratensian Eschatology: The Apocalyptic Myth”. In *The Spirituality of Western Christendom*,. Kalamazoo, MI: Cistercian Publications, 1976.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– I don't know

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Reference: Bandeniece, Beatrise. "Charity, Action and Contemplation : Twelfth-century Cistercian and Premonstratensian Teachings", 2017.

Reference: Lees, Jay T.. "Charity and Enmity in the Writings of Anselm of Havelberg" 25 (January 1994). <https://doi.org/10.1484/j.viator.2.301207>.

Reference: Melebeck, Charles. "Les Prémontrés Et La Charité : Un Hôpital Pour Assister Les Démonis". In Floreffe. Neuf Siècles D'histoire. Namur: Les éditions namuroises-ASBL Floreffe, 2021.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: While in theory all Christians were equal in Christ, as products of a hierarchical society, medieval Premonstratensians often referred to noble descent as positive and/or indicative of a certain kind of virtue.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Hope (spes) was regarded as a theological virtue by medieval Christians.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: Like all vowed religious, Premonstratensians were supposed to eschew worldly/sexual

attraction. According to her hagiographer one Premonstratensian sister, Oda of Rivreulle (d. 1158), disfigured her own face in order to escape the marriage her parents had planned for her and to be allowed to enter the religious life. However, there were still strong cultural associations between good and beauty and evil and ugliness and/or disability.

Reference: Robertson, Lynsey. "Philip of Harvengt's <i>life of the Blessed Virgin Oda</i>" 36, no. 1 (March 2010). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmedhist.2009.11.002>.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Masses and prayers were said annually for deceased members of the order, the number of which varied from community to community. According to the earliest surviving Premonstratensian ordinary, which was in use 13-14th centuries, specifies that for the first year after the death of a member of the order, he or she was to be prayed for daily, while each member of their community undertook a period of penance on their behalf. Vigil masses were to be celebrated on the 7th, 30th, and one-year anniversary of their death, while various memorial privileges were also celebrated in other Premonstratensian communities.

Reference: Lefèvre, Placide. *L'ordinaire De Prémontré D'après Des Manuscrits Du Xiie Et Du Xiiie Siècle*. Louvain: Bureaux de la Revue, 1941.

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Interment was the standard mode of burial for medieval Christians. Premonstratensian customs allowed for various people to be buried within the boundaries of one of their

communities: a member of the order, including those who joined ad succurendum (on their deathbed), those who were members of affiliated fraternities, those who died while within the boundaries of the monastic community, and those patrons of the community who expressed a wish to be buried in a Premonstratensian community.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Some members of the order, particularly heads of a community, might be buried with a seal-ring or seal-die or other symbol of office.

↳ Valuable items:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Some deceased members of the order were buried within the confines of their community's church itself, a burial location considered to be particularly spiritually efficacious.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Exists as part of a Trinity (Father, Son, Spirit); Creator God.

Notes: The tenets of Western Christian beliefs about the nature of the deity are laid out in e.g. the Nicene Creed.

Reference: The Council of Nicea. "The Nicene Creed", 1996.
<https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/source/nicene Creed.asp>.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Medieval Christians generally believed in the omniscience of God.

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: Mystical ecstasies; interpretation of signs and portents such as earthquakes, volcanic eruptions.
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - No
 - ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

- ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: Sodomy; extra-marital sex
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No
 - Notes: Dependent on context, e.g. jousting.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Yes, within medieval Christian understandings of social hierarchy/rank.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - No

- ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
 - No

- ↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
 - No

- ↳ Other purpose:
 - Yes [specify]: Mainstream Christian belief is that Jesus Christ was the Messiah, and that his eventual return will usher in a Messianic Age and the world to come.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time

would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

Reference: Bischoff, Guntram. “Early Premonstratensian Eschatology: The Apocalyptic Myth”. In *The Spirituality of Western Christendom*,. Kalamazoo, MI: Cistercian Publications, 1976.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Medieval Christian beliefs concerning the return of Jesus and the end of days varied. Some believed that the Second Coming was imminent, but the general belief was that the precise time would come like a “thief in the night” (1 Thess 5:2) and that no one knew the “day and hour” except for God the Father (Matt 24:36).

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Reference: Bandeniece, Beatrise. “Charity, Action and Contemplation : Twelfth-century Cistercian and Premonstratensian Teachings”, 2017.

Reference: Lees, Jay T.. “Charity and Enmity in the Writings of Anselm of Havelberg” 25 (January 1994). <https://doi.org/10.1484/j.viator.2.301207>.

Reference: Melebeck, Charles. “Les Prémontrés Et La Charité : Un Hôpital Pour Assister Les Démunis”. In Floreffe. Neuf Siècles D'histoire. Namur: Les éditions namuroises-ASBL Floreffe, 2021.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– I don't know

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– I don't know

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: While in theory all Christians were equal in Christ, as products of a hierarchical society, medieval Premonstratensians often referred to noble descent as positive and/or indicative of a certain kind of virtue.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Hope (spes) was regarded as a theological virtue by medieval Christians.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: Like all vowed religious, Premonstratensians were supposed to eschew worldly/sexual attraction. According to her hagiographer one Premonstratensian sister, Oda of Rivreulle (d. 1158), disfigured her own face in order to escape the marriage her parents had planned for her and to be allowed to enter the religious life. However, there were still strong cultural associations between good and beauty and evil and ugliness and/or disability.

Reference: Robertson, Lynsey. "Philip of Harvengt's <i>life of the Blessed Virgin Oda</i>" 36, no. 1 (March 2010). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmedhist.2009.11.002>.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: It requires celibacy (full sexual abstinence)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 3

Notes: Monastics were generally required to say the Divine Office at specified points during the day (Matins, Lauds, Prime, Terce, Sext, None, Vespers, and Compline). The exact times at which these prayers were recited depended according to season.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: However, small quantities of wine were consumed when receiving the sacrament of Communion.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: The Premonstratensians were often known as the White Canons, a reference to the colour of their habit.

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: The language of the Church (services, prayers, etc) during this period was Latin, which while still in active use as a language of learning was no longer a vernacular by the Middle Ages.

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: It requires celibacy (full sexual abstinence)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 3

Notes: Monastics were generally required to say the Divine Office at specified points during the day (Matins, Lauds, Prime, Terce, Sext, None, Vespers, and Compline). The exact times at which these prayers were recited depended according to season.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: However, small quantities of wine were consumed when receiving the sacrament of Communion.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: The Premonstratensians were often known as the White Canons, a reference to the colour of their habit.

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: The language of the Church (services, prayers, etc) during this period was Latin, which

while still in active use as a language of learning was no longer a vernacular by the Middle Ages.

- ↳ Other:
- No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
- Yes

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
- Yes

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
- No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Premonstratensians offered education at a number of levels: from a more elementary level in individual houses, to an advanced level at colleges or universities.

Reference: Ardura, Bernard. "Les Collèges De L'ordre De Prémontré, Du Moyen Âge Au Concile De Trente". In *Die Regulierten Kollegien Im Europa Des Mittelalters Und Der Renaissance*. Bochum: D. Winkler, 2012.

Reference: John, James J.. *The College of Prémontré in Mediaeval Paris*. Notre Dame, IN: Mediaeval Institute, University of Notre Dame, 1953.

- ↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:
- No

Notes: The order's medieval statutes imply that some communities provided at least an

elementary education to local children or children fostered in their care.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, however men tended to have more educational opportunities than did women.

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The Order was organised into circaries (regional groupings) which underwent regular visitations by circators, and also into filiations.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Premonstratensian communities frequently derived their income from the collection of tithes. Tithes could also be bought, sold, or exchanged to acquire additional income or to consolidate income sources, as was the case in 1246 when the Premonstratensian abbey of Drongen sold a number of tithes to Marguerite, Countess of Flanders.

Reference: Arkenberg, Jerome S., ed.. "Margaretta, Countess of Flanders & Hainault: A Purchase of Tithes and Remission of a Tax, 1246". Edited by Jerome S. Arkenberg, 1998.
<https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/source/1246prchtith.asp>.

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: During the order's main period of expansion in the 12th/13th centuries, it consolidated much of its landholdings in large agricultural units known as curtes (the equivalent of granges for other religious orders). The majority of these estates were given over to grain production, but the Premonstratensians also raised livestock, grew other crops, and engaged in fish farming.

Reference: Brunel, Chislain. "Agriculture Et Équipement Agricole À Prémontré (xiie-xiiiè Siècles)". In *Monachisme Et Technologie Dans La Société Médiévale Du Xe Au Xiiiè Siècle: Actes Du Colloque Scientifique International, Cluny 4, 5 Et 6 Septembre 1991*, edited by Charles Hetzlen. Cluny: Ecole nationale supérieure d'arts et métiers, 1994.

Reference: Abadie, Stéphane. "L'ordre De Prémontré En Agenais: Prieurés Et Granges Dépendant De L'abbaye Saint-jean De La Castelle". *Bulletin De La Société Académique D'agen* 146, no. 3 (2019): 273–95.

Reference: Bavel, Bas J.P. van. "Stichtingsplaats, Ontginning En Goederenverwerving. De Economische Ontwikkeling Van Norbertijner Abdijen in De Nederlanden (12de-13de Eeuw)". In *Ideaal En Werkelijkheid : Stichtingsplaatsen En Ontginningactiviteiten Van Premonstratenzers in De Nederlanden : Verslagen Van De Derde Contactdag Abdij Van Tongerlo, Zaterdag 15 Mei 1993*. Tongerlo: Abdij van Tongerlo, 1993.

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

- No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

- Yes

Notes: Like all medieval Christians, the Premonstratensian Order observed a formal calendar in the form of the liturgical year. The liturgical year was a cycle containing both seasons (such as Advent and Lent) and individual days (such as saints' days) to be marked. Calendars could vary regionally.

Reference: Placide, Lefèvre. *Études Sur La Liturgie De Prémontré*. Tongerlo: Imprimerie de l'abbaye, 1927.

Reference: Lefèvre, Placide. *La Liturgie De Prémontré: Histoire, Formulaire, Chant Et Cérémonial*. Louvain: Impr. E. Warny, 1957.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Premonstratensian communities could be given gifts of food or rights to part of a harvest by donors, particularly local lords or monarchs.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Premonstratensians observed the liturgical calendar of the Western Church with some regional variations for e.g. local saints' days.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The medieval Latin Church generally claimed exemption from secular legal prosecution/punishment, although various monarchs/polities did not always respect that claim.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Premonstratensian life was governed by the Augustinian Rule and also by various statutes laid out by the order's ruling bodies, primarily the General Chapter.

Reference: Dolista, Karel. *Acta Capitulum Triennialium Et Annalium Circariae Saxoniae Ordinis Praemonstratensis Inde Ab Anno 1466 Usque Ad Annum 1516*. Averbode, 1975.

Reference: Lefèvre, Placide. *Les Statuts De Prémontré Réformés Sur Les Ordres De Grégoire IX Et D'innocent IV Au Xiiie Siècle*. Louvain: Bibliothèque de l'Université, 1946.

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Reference: Valvekens, Johannes B.. Acta Et Decreta Capitulum Generalium Ordinis Praemonstratensis 4: 1588 - 1660. Averbode: Abbatia Averbodiensis, 1979.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Premonstratensians offered education at a number of levels: from a more elementary level in individual houses, to an advanced level at colleges or universities.

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Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: The order's medieval statutes imply that some communities provided at least an elementary education to local children or children fostered in their care.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, however men tended to have more educational opportunities than did women.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The Order was organised into circaries (regional groupings) which underwent regular visitations by circators, and also into filiations.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Premonstratensian communities frequently derived their income from the collection of tithes. Tithes could also be bought, sold, or exchanged to acquire additional income or to consolidate income sources, as was the case in 1246 when the Premonstratensian abbey of Drongen sold a number of tithes to Marguerite, Countess of Flanders.

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<https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/source/1246prchtith.asp>.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The medieval Latin Church generally claimed exemption from secular legal prosecution/punishment, although various monarchs/polities did not always respect that claim.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

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Notes: Premonstratensian life was governed by the Augustinian Rule and also by various statutes laid out by the order's ruling bodies, primarily the General Chapter.

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Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Like all medieval Christians, the Premonstratensian Order observed a formal calendar in the form of the liturgical year. The liturgical year was a cycle containing both seasons (such as Advent and Lent) and individual days (such as saints' days) to be marked. Calendars could vary regionally.

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Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Premonstratensians observed the liturgical calendar of the Western Church with some regional variations for e.g. local saints' days.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: During the order's main period of expansion in the 12th/13th centuries, it consolidated much of its landholdings in large agricultural units known as curtes (the equivalent of granges for other religious orders). The majority of these estates were given over to grain production, but the Premonstratensians also raised livestock, grew other crops, and engaged in fish farming.

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↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Premonstratensian communities could be given gifts of food or rights to part of a harvest by donors, particularly local lords or monarchs.

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Reference: *The Premonstratensian Order in the Middle Ages*, Backmund, Norbert. *Monasticon Praemonstratense*. De Gruyter, 1983. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110857962>.

Reference: *The Premonstratensian Order in the Middle Ages*, Antry, Theodore J.. *The Life of Saint Norbert: Founder of the Order of Prémontré : Vita Norberti B. Tehachapi, CA: The Norbertine Canonesses of the Bethlehem Priory of St. Joseph*, 2021.

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Plouvier, eds.. *Abbatia Et Abbés Dans L'ordre De Prémontré*. Edited by Dominique-Marie Dauzet and Martine Plouvier. Brepols Publishers, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.1484/m.bv-eb.6.09070802050003050106030302>.

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